
Financing of Housing Construction by Banks through Bonds

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Abstract: This article describes the financing mechanism of commercial banks for housing construction through corporate bonds. Also, the issue of securities, which is one of the ways to provide the necessary funds for housing construction during the construction period, the problems of its application in the banking sector of our country and their solutions are given.

Keywords: Issuer, housing construction financing, customer, contract construction organization, project-estimate documents, securities, order of housing construction, mortgage, authorized capital, balance sheet liabilities, bank loan, interest and discount rate, financing bank.

INTRODUCTION.

The development of the global corporate bond market and the accumulation of experience in using them to attract financial resources are expanding business opportunities and creating favorable conditions for economic growth. Bonds are one of the attractive instruments for obtaining borrowed funds by entrepreneurs, large companies and local governments. Bond issuance is considered a very flexible form of financing, since the issuer determines the parameters of the offer (interest rate, maturity, collateral).

Funds received from the placement of bonds can be used for current or investment activities. This is a viable alternative to bank lending for companies seeking debt financing. Corporate bonds, which are issued by large enterprises, are classified as fixed income securities and are a form of debt obligation to pay an agreed amount with interest at a certain time. Buyers of bonds can be individual and institutional investors who expect higher returns than from investments in government bonds and other securities, but do not want to take on the high risk of investing in stocks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

A number of foreign economists-scientists with the scientific-theoretical basis and practical issues of the development of housing construction financing process: Sh. Otman, O. Lavrushin, R. Shchenin, J. Kovgan, M. Wiemann, M. Shmit, Scientific works of M. Gritsenko and other scientists were studied. From local economist-scientists: T. Karaliev, A. Omonov, A. Vahobov, U. Azizov, Sh. Shokhazami, F. Dodiev, U. Elbusinova, J. Karimkulov, S. Elmirzaev, B. Sattorov, M. Mominov, D. Abdukarimova in his scientific researches, the development of the housing construction market, investments in securities in the banking system, and improvement of mortgage relations in the securities market were researched.

This article uses methods such as scientific interpretation, generalization and abstraction of theoretical data, statistical data processing, observation, systematization, comparison, induction and deduction.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

For development companies, issuing corporate bonds is just one way to get money to implement projects. This solution has many advantages and is an alternative to a bank loan. This method of

financing housing construction involves issuing corporate bonds of development companies. Interest in this instrument is growing every year, especially after the financial crisis of 2008-2009. The attractiveness of bonds is due to the flexibility and efficiency of using financial resources.

The favorable situation on the capital market makes it possible to refuse to issue bonds secured by real estate, so development companies choose unsecured securities. Investors, including commercial banks, attach importance mainly to the financial condition of the issuers, and not to the terms of the bond.

Obtaining a bank loan or bond issue is an interesting alternative to other sources of construction financing, especially for businesses seeking significant capital for development. A bond is a security issued in a series in which the issuer confirms that it is a debtor of the bondholder and undertakes to provide him with a certain financial benefit (repayment of the bond).

An issuer is defined as an entity that incurs obligations in the capital market by issuing bonds. Unlike shares, which give the right to participate in the assets of a company, a bond is a debt security, that is, an ordinary credit instrument like a bank loan to its issuer.

The most important features of bonds are as follows:

- Possibility of early repayment of bonds.
- Possibility of converting bonds into company shares and other privileges.
- The nature and method of financial compensation for the bondholder.

From the moment a bond is issued until maturity, this paper can change its owner many times. Each subsequent bond holder becomes a creditor of the issuer, that is, the construction company.

Issuing convertible bonds is especially beneficial for projects with good growth prospects. If such financing is attracted, the company's founders retain decisive influence on the direction of its development at the initial stage of the business. It is worth adding that the interest rate on convertible bonds may be lower compared to regular bonds.

Now we look at the differences for a construction organization between bonds and a bank loan. Thanks to the improving state of the sector, investors perceive corporate bonds of development companies as an attractive safe investment instrument. And vice versa, during periods of crisis in housing construction, the attractiveness of this instrument drops sharply.

Real estate represents the developer's primary asset, allowing bondholders to rely on debt repayment even if the developer gets into trouble. This is a common form of long-term financing for large developers, especially joint stock companies. The size of the bond issue can usually be larger than the bank's maximum loan amount, if only because of formal lending restrictions (for example, in relation to the debt concentration limit).

Bonds of development companies, characterized by good financial condition, are now a reliable investment. Their interest rate usually exceeds the yield on deposits offered by banks. Investors receive their interest regularly. In the event of a company's bankruptcy, debt holders claim various benefits to satisfy their financial claims.

1-figure. Main differences between a corporate bond and a bank loan¹

Funds from the sale of bonds are effectively used to finance priority investment projects specified in the terms of the issue of the corresponding corporate bonds. Bond proceeds are an “ideal example” of bridge financing. They can be an excellent additional source of financing to a loan, including providing the down payment required by banks. Debt securities are also convertible into shares.

As a classic example of bridge financing, corporate bonds of development companies are especially necessary in risky investment projects where banks require a significant contribution of their own. For example, financing the construction of multi-apartment buildings may require an initial deposit of approximately 30-50% of the total cost of the project.

¹ Prepared by the author on the basis of regulatory legal documents and information of commercial banks.

Developers often choose this form of financing because it allows them to purchase land for development and begin work without first selling assets. Issuing corporate bonds is a solution that has many advantages and is an alternative to debt.

For development companies, bonds mean a very convenient and fast way to raise money on the capital market, taking into account specific goals. This type of securities has been known for a long time, but is now becoming popular not only among institutional, but also among individual investors. There are a number of reasons for this.

Firstly, developer corporate bonds are issued in strict accordance with the current legislation of the host country. This provides investors with high reliability and security, especially when it comes to developed countries in Europe or North America with a strong legal system. On the other hand, companies remain completely free to choose how to issue bonds, targeting a broad pool of investors or only select individual investors.

Secondly, the bond issuer is required to indicate not only the purpose of the issue, but also its financial results, which guarantees transparency of both the offer and the issuer.

Third, developer bonds are considered to have much higher yields than treasury or municipal bonds.

However, it should be noted that the successful issue and placement of bonds of development companies highly depends on the trust in the developer, therefore this method of financing is chosen by well-known enterprises that have serious successes to their credit and work with recognizable business partners. In connection with The Ministry of Construction, the “Transparent Construction” platform was organized, which announces the rating of the construction potential of construction organizations. on this platform, house buyers can find out the reliability levels of developers.

For many companies in the sector, an important challenge is finding the capital needed to finance large housing projects and business development. Financing construction using external capital is due to the fact that such projects require large expenses, and not all investors have sufficient funds at a certain time. The issue and placement of corporate bonds is the optimal source of long-term financing, leading to overcoming the shortage of capital.

*2-figure. The process of financing housing construction by a commercial bank through bonds*²

The issue of corporate bonds is one of the promising mechanisms that can be used to finance both operating and investment activities. The issue of corporate bonds can be used to solve the following problems:

- Attracting financial resources to cover the short-term cash deficit required for investment in working capital; covering the medium-term or long-term shortage of funds necessary for the implementation of investments in fixed capital;
- Restructuring of an enterprise in order to change the ownership structure or improve financial performance (for example, takeover of competitors, closure of unpromising branches, subsidiaries, decommissioning of ineffective assets);
- Financial restructuring of the company, including the formation of liquid collateral in the form of securities, securitization of assets, debt restructuring, raising funds for financial recovery;
- Achieving other marketing goals (for example, attracting attention to the brand, advertising, public assessment of the company by financial analysts);
- Formation of a positive stock exchange and credit history of the business to obtain more favorable financing conditions in world markets and within the country;
- Financial engineering activities to solve current or long-term financial problems using complex financial mechanisms.

The terms of placement of corporate bonds depend on the chosen placement method and the specific market targeted by the issuer. Attracting financial resources through the placement of corporate bonds complies with the five listed principles. Principles of using corporate bonds to finance business:

1. Competitive nature of financing. From the point of view of the volume of placement and the cost of attracted financial resources, the success of the issue of corporate bonds is determined by the ratio of supply and demand in the financial market;
2. One-time placement. When placing corporate bonds, the issuing company attracts all financial resources almost instantly in a short period of time, rather than in separate sequential tranches;
3. Use of professional intermediaries. The complexity of the issue is determined by the significant volume of attracted financial resources and the issuer's interest in maximizing the expansion of the circle of bond owners;
4. Use of exchange infrastructure. This principle involves the placement, circulation and redemption of corporate bonds using the exchange infrastructure, which allows minimizing the costs of market participants;
5. Fixed debt service. Payment of coupons and redemption of the face value of corporate bonds are carried out with fixed and predetermined parameters, which ensures the predictability of the issuer's debt servicing costs and the predictability of investor returns.

The issue of corporate bonds seems to be very appropriate for construction companies acting as property developers. A large developer builds objects for sale, that is, he needs financial resources for a limited period from the construction of the object to its sale to the final buyer.

Since the developer does not remain the owner of the property in the future, he usually faces the problem of not having collateral for each subsequent bank loan. Another problem for such issuers is the high cost of financial resources, because it is growing as a result of declining profitability in the commercial and residential real estate construction market.

² Prepared by the author on the basis of regulatory legal documents and information of commercial banks.

Raising capital for the construction of large projects with the help of corporate bonds allows developers to minimize dependence on bank loans and sell off unfinished real estate in the early stages. The use of this instrument allows business entities to obtain funds for the purchase of equipment by mobilizing funds from private investors without involving expensive instruments, as is done during leasing.

Below we will discuss such an important point for market participants as potential restrictions on the use of bonds, risks and ways to minimize them. Risks of the agent bank for issuing corporate bonds.

The risk of issue failure can be neutralized by an agent bank that actively supports the issuer, focusing its activities not only on the primary, but also on the secondary market. By actively participating in the issue, a large agent is able to take on almost all types of risks to which the issuer is exposed.

Agents are typically financial institutions, including banks that provide investment banking services as part of corporate banking. Although the intermediation of banks increases the cost of attracted capital, it guarantees the issuer professional preparation and profitable placement of bonds on the market. A bank that provides services for organizing the issue of corporate bonds and other debt instruments can simultaneously assume the role of depository and paying agent. One of the services provided by agents is the provision of bank guarantees, which relate to underwriting, bond redemption and redemption.

The most common models for assuming the risk of a bond issue have become firm commitment underwriting or best efforts underwriting. In the first case, the guarantor undertakes to buy from the issuer at his own expense all the securities that are the subject of the agreement, with a view to their subsequent sale.

In a “best efforts” case, the guarantor agrees to use its best efforts to distribute the issue to investors without committing itself to repurchase them. This decision means that the risk of failure of the issue falls on the issuer, and the guarantor plays only the role of an active sales agent. If the inflow of funds from the issue decreases, the guarantor can take upon himself the organization of an investment loan for the issuer, looking for investors who are ready to take on the entire issue.

A buyback guarantee, on the other hand, obliges the financial institution to maintain liquidity in the secondary securities market. It comes down to the role of a market maker, which is expressed in the constant receipt of orders and stimulation of demand.

Thus, the agent bank becomes a party to the transaction. Taking care of stabilizing the appropriate level of price and liquidity of bonds, he receives income from the margin received. A buyback guarantee means a transfer of credit risk from investors to the bank providing the guarantee. It also protects the issuing agent from the reputational risk to investors that may arise if the bonds are not redeemed on the primary market.

CONCLUSION.

The issuance of corporate bonds plays an important role in raising capital by companies around the world. The characteristics of corporate bonds in different conditions can become both advantages and disadvantages for issuers.

1-table. Advantages and disadvantages of issuing corporate bonds to finance large business projects³

Advantages	Disadvantages
Wide range of potential investors	A very stable financial position of the company is required
Attracting significant financial resources for a long period (more than a year)	Significant costs associated with organizing the issue and disclosing financial information
Lack of strict requirements for the intended use of raised capital	Limitation of the use of capital for the formation of authorized capital, as well as for covering company losses
Increasing the authority of the company as a whole	The need to repay the principal amount with interest
Minimal project dependence on one lender and reduced risk concentration	High costs of organizing the first placement of corporate bonds
Attracting cheap financial resources from a variety of private and institutional investors in the public market	Regular expenses of the issuer associated with payment for the services of the depository, underwriters, rating agencies, auditors, etc.
The most flexible principal and interest repayment models	Lengthy and complex procedure
Minimizing debt servicing costs through flexible issuance terms	Risk of permanent loss of funds in case of unsuccessful bond placement
Expanding capabilities for financial, tax and production planning	Increase in the cost of attracted capital in the event of a decrease in interest rates on the market
Formation of a positive credit history and exchange reputation of the issuer	Risk of decline in key indicators of the issuer's financial stability
Extensive opportunities for financial engineering using the most advanced tools	Quite a complex and lengthy formal procedure for attracting financial resources
Increasing the investment attractiveness of the issuer and a specific project through the disclosure of financial information and external monitoring	Reduced financial mobility and profitability of the issuing company due to the need to reserve funds for payments to bondholders
Individual assessment of the attractiveness of the offer by investors	High cost of financing

It can be seen from the above that there are a number of advantages and disadvantages of financing construction organizations by placing bonds of developers in commercial banks.

However, although this financing mechanism has shortcomings, it is appropriate to implement it in the development of the construction market of Uzbekistan. Because commercial banks offer a wide range of financing to construction organizations, the housing construction market grows both quantitatively and qualitatively. In turn, the assets of commercial banks are diversified and the level of riskiness decreases.

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